

Supporting Information

A New Label-Free Approach to Glioblastoma Cancer Stem Cell

sorting and detection.

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Proof Version

SI 1: Phenotypical characterization

Western blotting

Cells were suspended in lysis buffer (Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, MA, USA) at 4°C for 30 min. After centrifugation for 15 min at 10,000 *g*, protein in the supernatant was quantified by the Bradford method. SDS-PAGE was performed with 30 µg of protein (or 5 µg of protein after SdFFF sorting). Resolved proteins were transferred onto PVDF membranes (Millipore SAS, Molsheim, France), which were blocked in 5% non-fat dry milk prepared in TBS-T (TBS containing 0.1% Tween-20) for 1 h and then incubated overnight with various primary antibodies. Anti-CD133/1, anti-CD133/2, and anti-A2B5 (Miltenyi Biotec, 1:50 dilution) as well as anti-OCT-4 (Thermo Scientific, Illkirch, France 1:450 dilution) primary antibodies were used. After three washes with TBS-T, membranes were incubated for 1 h with peroxidase-conjugated IgG (H + L) diluted 1:1000 in 5% non-fat dry milk prepared in TBS-T and then washed another three times. POD activity was detected using Immobilon Western Chemiluminescent HRP Substrate (Millipore) and quantified on a G-Box (Syngene, Cambridge, UK).

Analysis of cell size using a Coulter counter and proteome array

A 256-channel Multisizer II Coulter counter (Beckman Coulter, Fullerton, CA, USA) was used to determine the mean cell diameter in a population. Cells were diluted in Isoton[®] to a final volume of 15 mL. The sample volume was 500 µL, and the results of three successive assays were combined. Results are displayed as means ± standard deviation of three independent experiments.

The Human Pluripotent Stem Cell Array Kit (R&D Systems, Minneapolis, MN, USA) was used to analyze expression of CSC markers. Protein expression levels in sorted and unsorted samples were evaluated according to the manufacturer's instructions. Capture and control antibodies (15 stem cell markers and three standards) were spotted in duplicate onto nitrocellulose membranes. Cell extracts (50 μg) were incubated with the membranes overnight. The arrays were washed to remove unbound proteins and then incubated with a cocktail of biotinylated detection antibodies. Streptavidin-HRP and chemiluminescent detection reagents were applied. The signal produced at each spot corresponded to the amount of bound protein. After incubation, membranes were developed using enhanced chemiluminescence reagents and quantified on a G-Box. Protein expression was normalized against a positive control present on each membrane.

Acquisition of confocal z-stacks to determine N:C ratios

NN, NH, DN, and DH subpopulations were sub-cultured in LabTek chambers (5000 cells) under previously described conditions. The N:C ratio in each condition was determined by assembling confocal z-stacks on a Zeiss LSM 510 META microscope controlled by associated Velocity software. This is the ratio between the cytoplasmic and nuclear volumes. Cells were incubated for 30 min with the vital probes Calcein-AM (10 μM) and DRAQ5™ (10 nM) to detect total cells and morphological features of nuclei, respectively. Velocity software enabled direct measurement of the nuclear volume in samples counterstained with DRAQ5. The cytoplasmic volume (in μm^3) was obtained by subtracting the nuclear volume (in μm^3) from the total cell volume (in μm^3), which was determined based on Calcein-AM fluorescence.

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SI-2: Functional tests

Cell proliferation assay (BrdU incorporation)

BrdU is a synthetic nucleoside analog of thymidine that is incorporated into newly synthesized DNA in S-phase cells. BrdU incorporation is commonly used as an index of proliferation. To measure proliferation using the BrdU Cell Proliferation Assay Kit (Cell Signaling Technology), 1000 cells were incubated with 10 μ M BrdU in a 96-well plate for 4 h at 37°C to permit incorporation of the nucleoside analog. After centrifugation, cells were fixed and denatured for 30 min. An anti-BrdU antibody was added, and the sample was incubated for 1 h and rinsed three times. The HRP-conjugate antibody solution was added, and the sample was washed as described above. Finally, the HRP substrate TMB was added, and the sample was incubated for 30 min, by which time the reaction had stopped. Absorbance was measured at 450 nm.

Clonogenicity assay on Matrigel

Clonogenicity assays were performed to determine the ability of cells to proliferate indefinitely (*i.e.*, to form a clone). In these experiments, 5000 cells were seeded into 12-well plates containing Growth Factor-Reduced Matrigel Matrix (BD Biosciences, Le Pont de Claix, France) and then covered with the appropriate culture medium. Colonies were grown for 4 weeks at 37°C in a humidified environment containing 5% CO₂ with or without hypoxia. Visible colonies were counted and measured using ImageJ³⁴.

SI-3: Preparation of magnetic CD133/1 beads for cell separation

Cells expressing CD133, a marker of CSCs, were selected and separated by retaining CD133-positive cells on a column of magnetic CD133/1 beads. After centrifugation, cells were suspended in 300 μ L of R buffer (PBS, pH 7.2, supplemented with 0.5% bovine serum albumin and 2 mmol/L EDTA). Thereafter, 100 μ L of FcR reagent (Miltenyi Biotec, Skedsmokorset, Norway) was added to inhibit non-specific and Fc receptor-mediated binding of antibodies to non-target cells. Next, 100 μ L of CD133/1 MicroBeads was added to label the cells, which were then mixed and incubated for 30 min at 4°C. Thereafter, cells were washed by addition of R buffer and centrifugation at 300 *g* for 10 min. The supernatant was discarded. Cell pellets were resuspended in 500 μ L of R buffer. A medium-size column was placed in the magnetic field of the magnetic-activated cell separation separator and rinsed with 0.5 mL of R buffer. The cell suspension was applied to the column, which was then washed three times with 0.5 mL of R buffer. The column was then removed from the separator and placed on a collection tube. Finally, 1 mL of R buffer was pipetted onto the column, and the positive fraction containing magnetically labeled CD133/1 cells was firmly flushed out (using the plunger supplied with the column) and preserved for analysis.

Figure SI-1: Expression of OCT-4, a stem cell marker, after CD133/1-positive magnetic cell sorting. Western blot was performed using 30 μ g of total protein per lane. *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure SI-2. SdFFF cell sorting enriches cells positive for stem cell markers regardless of the cell culture conditions. Expression of stem cell proteins were quantified in comparison with the internal control provided by the manufacturer (proteome array).

Fig SI-3: Quantification of OCT-4, a CSC marker, by the proteome array before and after cell sorting using SdFFF. *** $p < 0.001$.

Figure SI-4: The N:C ratio before cell sorting. Nuclear and cytoplasmic volumes of cells cultured in NN, NH, DN, and DH conditions were measured using deconvolution software after confocal analysis. The cytoplasmic volume:nuclear volume ratios are plotted.

Figure SI-5: Colonies (gliomaspheres) derived from DH F1 (A) and DH F3 (B) after SdFFF cell sorting in the clonogenicity assay on Matrigel. Light microscopy (bright field) images demonstrate that the size and number of colonies are higher in DH F3 (A) than in DH F1 (B). The density and number of colonies were quantified by ImageJ. Scale bars correspond to 250 μm .

Table SI-1: Measurement of U87-MG cell density. Density gradient centrifugation of U87-MG cells was performed. Fifteen solutions (G_0 to G_{15}) with different densities and containing different concentrations of *Iodixanol* (OptiPrep™) were prepared. Pelleted cells corresponded to those whose density was higher than that of the medium, while retained cells corresponded to those whose density was lower than that of the medium.

Gradient	Density	% of Iodixanol	Cell behavior
Gradient 0	PBS 1×	0% (control)	Pelleted cells
Gradient 1	1.037	6%	Pelleted cells
Gradient 2	1.043	7%	Pelleted cells
Gradient 3	1.048	8%	Pelleted cells
Gradient 4	1.053	9%	Pelleted cells
Gradient 5	1.058	10%	Suspended cells (upper layers)
Gradient 6	1.064	11%	Suspended cells (upper layers)
Gradient 7	1.069	12%	Retained cells
Gradient 8	1.074	13%	Retained cells
Gradient 9	1.079	14%	Retained cells
Gradient 10	1.085	15%	Retained cells
Gradient 11	1.090	16%	Retained cells
Gradient 12	1.095	17%	Retained cells
Gradient 13	1.100	18%	Retained cells
Gradient 14	1.105	19%	Retained cells
Gradient 15	1.110	20%	Retained cells

Table SI-2. To obtain the EM signature, we used a simplified **Cole-Cole Model**³⁵ provided by the following equation:

$$\epsilon_{r_Cell}(\omega) = \frac{\Delta\epsilon_r(1 + (\omega\tau)^{1-\alpha} \sin(\alpha\pi/2))}{1 + 2(\omega\tau)^{1-\alpha} \sin(\alpha\pi/2) + (\omega\tau)^{2-\alpha}} + \epsilon_{r,\infty}$$

where ω is the angular frequency (*i.e.*, $\omega = 2\pi f$) and $\epsilon_{r,\infty}$, $\Delta\epsilon_r$, τ , and α are variable parameters chosen to fit the experimental data. The **Cole-Cole Model** parameters considered to establish the EM signatures of the investigated cell subpopulations are provided in the following tables.

Parameter	NN-CC	NH-CC	DN-CC	DH-CC
$\epsilon_{r,\infty}$	2	2	2	2
$\Delta\epsilon$	120	120	120	120
τ	32 ps	26 ps	20ps	16 ps
α	0.001	0.07	0.05	0.01

Parameter	NN F1-CC	NN F3-CC	DH F1-CC	DH F3 -CC
$\epsilon_{r,\infty}$	2	2	2	2
$\Delta\epsilon$	120	130	120	130
τ	47 ps	30 ps	22 ps	15 ps
α	0.001	0.001	0.05	0.005